

Title: The BINGO Radio Telescope: an instrument to investigate the Universe through the 21 cm neutral hydrogen line

Thematic areas: Cosmology, Dark Energy, Astronomy & Astrophysics

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Webpage of the project: <https://portal.if.usp.br/bingotelescope/pt-br>

Abstract: BINGO is a unique radio telescope designed to make the first detection of Baryon Acoustic Oscillations (BAO) at radio frequencies. This will be achieved by measuring the distribution of neutral hydrogen gas (HI) at cosmological distances using a technique called Intensity Mapping. Along with the Cosmic Microwave Background anisotropies, the scale of BAO is one of the most powerful probes of cosmological parameters, including dark energy. The telescope will be built in a very low RFI site in Aguiar (Paraíba), in Northeastern Brazil (coordinates Lat:7° 2' 29" S; Lon: 38° 16' 30" W). It will operate in the frequency range from 0.98 GHz to 1.26 GHz. The telescope design consists in a compact, crossed-Dragone configuration with two 40-m compact mirrors and no moving parts. Such a design will give the excellent polarization performance and very low sidelobe levels required for HI intensity mapping. With a feedhorn array of 50 receivers, it will map a 15° declination strip as the sky drifts past the field-of-view of the telescope. The BINGO consortium is coordinated by the Universidade de São Paulo, and co-led by Instituto Nacional de Pesquisas Espaciais and Universidade Federal de Campina Grande (Brazil) and has the University of Manchester and University College London (United Kingdom), ETH Zürich (Switzerland), Yang Zhou University (China) and University of KwaZulu-Natal (South Africa) as foreign partners. The receiver, including the horns and all the electronics, is mostly ready for fabrication and the mirrors and the telescope structure are in the final design and construction project phases. The data analysis pipeline and science forecasts are being led by a Brazilian team and we expect to deliver a number of papers in 2020 regarding the simulation of BINGO science capabilities. BINGO will also have a strong synergy with a number of optical and radio instruments that will visit parts of the BINGO observed patch in the sky (~ 5400 square degrees) allowing for an immediate multiwavelength approach for BINGO data analysis.

Proposal Overview

Scientific context

The BINGO (BAO from Integrated Neutral Gas Observations) project is a double dish radio telescope designed to observe the 21cm line emission from neutral hydrogen in a redshift interval $0.13 < z < 0.48$ (corresponding to a frequency interval $1260 < f < 980$). It will cover a sky patch of about 5400 square degrees ($\sim 1/8$ of the sky) with an angular resolution of 40 arcmin and will use two, 40-m diameter, reflectors and a focal plane with 50 detectors, covering an instantaneous patch of the sky with about 30 square degrees. Assuming that the hydrogen distribution is a fair tracer of matter distribution in the Universe, even taking a known HI bias into account, BINGO will be in a very good position of producing a detailed tomography of the matter distribution in the Universe in the visited redshift interval, including data from Baryon Acoustic Oscillations (BAO). **Fine measurements of BAO in the BINGO redshift range, which covers the last half of the expansion history, can be extremely useful to set constraints in the current understanding of Dark Energy (DE) properties.**

Usually, large scale structure maps of the Universe are conducted through analysis of galaxy surveys. This approach allows for a detailed overview of small patches of the sky (a few tens to a few hundreds of square degrees) and requires the measurement of individual properties of galaxies. An alternative approach, proposed in the 2000's, is the measurement of the collective 21 cm emission of the underlying hydrogen distribution around large concentrations of galaxies, through a technique known as Intensity Mapping (IM). It allows the fast surveying of a much broader sky patch using radio telescopes with very large collecting area, yielding a straight relationship between observed frequency and redshift of the emitting source, in detriment of losing the fine details of the emitting sources. By observing the intensity fluctuations one gathers information about the matter power spectrum, and use HI as a tracer of the 3-D large scale structure of the Universe. This approach does not require additional information about underlying structures (galaxies) facilitating greatly the observation and data taking.

In order to have a statistical precision less than 1% in the observations, galactic as well as extragalactic foregrounds with intensity as large as 10^4 times the HI signal have to be removed. However, their smooth frequency dependency allows for quite

an efficient separation approach. BINGO is an excellent ground for testing different separation methods for HI intensity mapping, allowing for a possible, and quite useful and interesting, pathfinder to the upcoming Square Kilometre Array – SKA telescope.

Objectives

1. Measuring BAO in the redshift range $0.13 < z < 0.48$
2. Investigate redshift space distortions
3. Characterize synchrotron polarization in the frequency range $980 < f < 1260$
4. Investigate the current case for the anomalous cosmic radio background detected by the ARCADE instrument

Methodology

Use measurements of the galaxy distribution, weak lensing, supernova and cluster counts to find

the best parameters that describe the data in a given theoretical model in a bayesian framework.

List of interested scientists

At this moment there are 5 Principal Investigators (PI) in the BINGO steering committee:

1. Elcio Abdalla (USP)
2. Luciano Barosi Lemos (UFCG)
3. Richard Battye (Univ. Manchester)
4. Bin Wang (Yang Zhou University)
5. Carlos Alexandre Wuensche (INPE)

And the scientists (staff and pos-docs) listed in the BINGO Management Guidelines documents, approved in the BINGO Critical Design Review (July 08 – 10, 2019) follow below. Note that M.Sc. and Ph.D students are not included in this list.

USP	INPE	UFCG	Univ. of Manchester
Elisa Ferreira	Alan Cassiano	Alexandre Jean René Serres	Adrian Galtress
Karin Fornazier	Camila Novaes	Amilcar Queiróz	Clive Dickinson
Ricardo Landim	César Strauss	Douglas Fregolente	Ian Browne
Andreia de Souza	Cristiane Zavatti	Edmar Candeia Gurjão	Keith Grange
	Ivan Barbosa	Eduardo Passos	Mathieu Remazeilles
	Luiz Reitano	Francisco Brito	Peter Dewdney

	Renato Branco	João Maria da Silva	Peter Wilkinson
	Thyrso Villela	João Rafael Lucio dos Santos	Ralph Spencer
	Vincenzo Liccardo	Marcos Anacleto	Stuart Harper
		Victor Ignacio Afonso	
UCL	IFPB	UFPB	UFPE
Filipe Abdalla	Emmanuel Dupouy	Antônio Augusto de Souza	Bruno Carneiro da Cunha
	Carlos Alex Souza da Silva		
UnB	IAP	YangZhou University	Teide Observatory
Ivan Soares Ferreira	Bruno Maffei	Larissa Santos	Michael Peel
	Sambit Roychowdury	André Alencar da Costa	
Shanghai Jiao Tong University	Univ. KwaZulu-Natal	Universidade de Aveiro	ETH
Haiguang Xu	YinZhe Ma	Sonia Antón	Christian Monstein
Jie Zhu			Alexandre Refregier
U. Harvard	NASA	Uruguay	
Emilio Falco	Ana Mosquera	Santiago Tezanos	

Current status, timeline and expected challenges

- BINGO has its receiver prototype almost completely built.
- Horns and *front end* have been designed, tested and approved in the electromagnetic verification at INPE
- Detector components have been tested at INPE and are waiting for filters and low noise amplifiers to arrive, in order to assemble a full correlation receiver for tests in the lab.
- Digital backend needs more attention in the upcoming months for full programming and operationalization.
- Optical design is close to completion. Horn positioning and final structure design have been already calculated. Next steps: structural analysis of the horn focal plane array and mirror support structures.
- Mirrors being quoted in the Brazilian industries.
- BINGO data analysis pipeline is under construction. Mission simulation and component separation modules are 85% functional. Modules for non-gaussian identification and cosmological analysis are under construction (about 50% completed).
- Terrain is already being cleaned for foundation positioning and civil work is expected to start no later than April 01, 2020.
- Expected data storage needs for BINGO are about 80 TB/year for final products and about 500 TB/year for processing space

- Timeline for BINGO is as follows:
 - Site cleaning and beginning of construction: no later than April 01, 2020
 - INPE Data Center is being contacted to supply the necessary expertise for data stewardship. Expected support and operational conditions expected to be laid in an internal agreement no later than June 01, 2020.
 - Structural analysis of the BINGO structure: results are expected no later than August 31, 2020
 - Assembling of the metal structure for the horn focal plane and mirrors: starting no later than October 01, 2020
 - Deployment of mirrors and receivers to the site: no later than 1 month after assembling is completed. Expected date: no later than March 31, 2021.
 - Expected commissioning configuration: no less than 5 detectors (horns + front end + receiver chain + digital back + data acquisition software + data processing software) and mirrors in place, with operation cabin and internet connection no later than April 30, 2021.
 - First commissioning actions: starting no later than May 31, 2021.

Construction and operational costs

Money for the construction and operational costs for the LSST has already been granted by FAPESP, FINEP, MCTIC and a smaller fraction of foreign contribution (mostly purchasing components for the telescope construction).